

Mathematical Modeling of Under-Sampled data: Case Study of COVID-19 cases

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Abstract: Under-sampling (under reported or under estimated) in reported cases is frequently observed in any pandemic scenario indicated by many healthcare researchers. The effect of this issue is not only reducing the acceptance of the presented statistics but also might fail possible prediction of future infection rates, spreading frequency, estimated causalities, etc. during the pandemic. Thus, this study aims to present a way of determining under-sampled data through mathematical solutions. In this study, we particularly present our preliminary case study considering a single day reported COVID-19 cases for the year 2021. To do the statistical observation, we incorporated several mathematical equations and the standard deviation (SD) technique. The outcome of this work will help to identify the under-sampled data not only for the COVID-19 cases but also will be effective for other pandemic data.

Keywords: COVID-19 cases, mathematical observation, standard deviation, Under-sampling, prediction/estimation.

Introduction

COVID-19 was caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, first being confirmed in China in December 2019 [1]. In March 2020, the World Health Organization declared it as a global pandemic. Since January 2020, researchers collected reports of COVID-19 cases to identify the confirmed cases to estimate the future ratio of the infected case within the population. In many countries, the number of detected or confirmed cases as a proportion of the total population was underestimated [2]. This might happen due to an inadequate number of testing facilities. Thus, it is difficult to identify the true/actual number of infected population rates which raises issues related to the under-sampling problem. According to the researcher's opinion, the true affection rate might be three or four times higher due to under reporting [3]. Therefore, identification of the true infection rate is an urgent aspect for the healthcare researcher. Nowadays, it's become an

important health priority to people as data collection is still unreliable which hampers the estimation of true infection rate. Several past studies suggested that COVID-19 is a widespread viral disease that can spread widely, but the detection rate is limited, which could be a disaster [4].

Nowadays, there are several web pages providing statistics on COVID-19, including the ratio of confirmed cases, deaths, recovered, how many people are in serious condition, and other aspects. Among several sources of COVID-19 cases, WORLDOMETER is the most popular and reliable to people around the world. Recently, some countries started to provide information about recent COVID-19 statistics through their web pages, for example, ¹Our World in Data. The majority of the resources generate statistics such as infected cases based on the number of tests, either positive or negative. However, apart from this, other aspects might be responsible for unbiased estimation/result. Among several issues, routinely collected data that is a feasible task can be biased in the estimation of the total number of cases, death ratio, recovered rate, etc [5]. Therefore, it is challenging and essential to identify what the existing estimation challenges are.

During the early stage of the pandemic, there were some controversial opinions among researchers and healthcare scientists about which casualties should be considered in predicting the actual affected rate. At first, people associated with healthcare have taken into consideration the daily number of infections and the transmission rate from infectious to recovered. Some other perspectives have been taken into consideration, such as people who are close to the affected person and the other associated person with the affected people. All the considered aspects could generate unbiased estimation, and it is hard to obtain true statistics from this observation [6]. Thus, in this work, we present statistical analysis or statistical interpretation process to analyze the collected data or COVID-19 data to identify or interpret the possible reported cases that provide under-sampled data.

In the following sections, the related literature and the methodology with the statistical observation is presented by emphasizing under-sampling/reported/estimated data. Also in this section, we added some implications that need to be considered further and lastly, a conclusion is added to present the summary of the work with future focus.

Related literature

To represent the effects of COVID-19, several works have presented their contribution focusing on a wide array of aspects. Most of the studies

¹ <https://ourworldindata.org/>

emphasized the importance of the compartment model for the analysis of COVID-19 data by highlighting several advantages of this technique [7]. Following this, Abou-Ismael [8] presents several compartment models and concludes that compartment models are effective for analyzing and understanding several crucial aspects related to epidemiology. Addressing this aspect few works have been done focusing on several compartment models. For example, Hamzah et al. [9] analyzed COVID-19 data to predict and forecast COVID-19 cases, deaths, and recoveries using the Susceptible-Exposed-Infectious-Recovered (SEIR) predictive model. Following this work, Shapiro et al. [10] also implemented the same SEIR model to estimate the infection rate and reproduction number in terms of varying time. Their investigation was particularly for COVID-19 cases in the USA. In another work, Hou et al. [11] analyzed the effectiveness of the quarantine in Uhan City China using the SEIR model and also, they presented several statistical observations to support their analysis. However, these models are effective in analyzing the effects, future situations, and impacts of COVID-19, but none of the work focused on the effect of under-sampled data of COVID-19 cases. Besides, few researchers emphasized future investigation of the effect of under-sampled cases [12]. Thus, it is crucial to investigate the reported COVID-19 cases to identify the under-sampled data and their effects.

Method

This section aims to present the statistical interpretation of collected COVID-19 data with the focus of representing possible under-sampled data. This section is organized to present details about dataset information and several mathematical and statistical observation processes including the unique findings and clear discussion for supporting the findings.

Dataset description

In this work, we used COVID-19 data that was collected from the Kaggle database. This dataset is available on the ²Kaggle website and prepared by scraping data from the COVID-19 tracking website named ³Worldometer for a three-day report that was recorded from 4/8/2021 to 6/8/2021. However, for this work, we used only one day of reported data that was recorded on 4/8/2021. This dataset contains 21 features or attributes.

² <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/stevenlasch/worldometer-covid-dataset>

³ <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>

Statistical observation

In order to do our statistical observation, we analyzed the dataset in the Python programming language. According to the dataset description, the dataset contains 21 features, however, according to the aim of this work, we consider six attributes such as Country, Confirmed cases, Deaths, Recovered, Active cases, and Test number, and eliminate the remaining features from the analysis. To do the statistical analysis, we consider the number of total cases ($I(t)$), total death ($D(t)$), total recovered ($R(t)$), and active cases ($A(t)$) to identify the unbiased estimation. Considering these features, we calculated the number of closed cases [equation-1], the ratio of death [equation-2], the ratio of recovered [equation-3], and the ratio of active cases [equation-4]. Besides, we also tried to compute the effect of total death in terms of total recovered people [equation-5] and the effect of death and active cases in terms of total cases [equation-6]. All these computations are performed through some mathematical equations that are given below:

$$\text{ClosedCases} = D(t) + R(t) \text{ -- [1]}$$

**total number of death $D(t)$, total number of recovered $R(t)$

$$\text{Ratio of death } d(t) = \frac{D(t)}{I(t)} * 100 \text{ -- [2]}$$

** total number of death $D(t)$, number of total cases $I(t)$

$$\text{Ratio of recovered } r(t) = \frac{R(t)}{I(t)} * 100 \text{ -- [3]}$$

** total number of recovered $R(t)$, number of total cases $I(t)$

$$\text{Ratio of active cases } a(t) = \frac{A(t)}{I(t)} * 100 \text{ -- [4]}$$

** total number of active cases $A(t)$, number of total cases $I(t)$

$$\text{effect of death cases } (d) = \frac{D(t)}{D(t) + R(t)} \text{ -- [5]}$$

$$\text{effect of death and active cases } (d, a) = \frac{D(t) + A(t)}{D(t) + A(t) + R(t)} \text{ -- [6]}$$

After performing all the calculations and obtaining ratios, we observed the mean difference among the calculated data to understand their

significant difference among other data. To identify the significant differences in the data, we used the standard deviation technique also known as SD. It is the measurement of the variation of a set of data where low SD indicates the lower dispersion and higher SD indicates the significant dispersion among the data. The equation of SD is shown in equation 7.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \mu)^2}{N}} \quad \text{--- [7]}$$

We conducted the significance analysis among three independent groups: G-1 (death and recovered cases), G-2 (recovered and active cases), and G-3 (death and active cases). All the computed data through the equations and their observed SD values for three individual groups are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Computed statistics of COVID-19 cases per country

Country	Ratio of Death (d(t))	Ratio of recovered (r(t))	Ratio of active (a(t))	SD [d(t), r(t)]	SD [r(t), a(t)]	SD [d(t), a(t)]	Effect (d)	Effect (d, a)
USA	1.74849	82.51236	15.73913	40.381935	33.386615	6.99532	0.02075	0.17487
India	1.34018	97.34725	1.31256	48.003535	48.017345	0.01381	0.01358	0.02652
Brazil	2.79493	93.79964	3.40542	45.502355	45.19711	0.305245	0.02893	0.06200
Russia	2.54397	89.35087	8.10515	43.40345	40.62286	2.78059	0.02768	0.10649
France	1.81258	92.54040	5.64701	45.36391	43.446695	1.917215	0.01921	0.07459
UK	2.18386	76.72943	21.08670	37.27278	27.821365	9.45142	0.02767	0.23270
Turkey	0.89109	94.41693	4.69197	46.76292	44.86248	1.90044	0.00934	0.05583
Argentina	2.14529	92.82824	5.02646	45.341475	43.90089	1.440585	0.02258	0.07171
Colombia	2.52671	95.80199	1.67128	46.63764	47.065355	0.427715	0.02569	0.04198
Spain	1.80067	82.74628	15.45303	40.472805	33.646625	6.82618	0.02129	0.17253
Italy	2.93219	94.84306	2.22473	45.955435	46.309165	0.35373	0.02998	0.05156

To identify the under-sampled data, we analyze these data (d(t), r(t), and a(t)) in two steps. First, we compared the differences among computed data to identify their significant difference among the three groups of data. Later, we compared the differences among computed data to identify their significant difference in terms of their effects on death and active cases.

Figure 1 shows the representation of SD values of three groups that helps us to understand the significant differences among the data. It indicates that in the three groups, a significant difference was found for data from the USA, UK, and Spain and the differences among the remaining data were not significant enough to mention. Besides, Figure 2 shows the computed

statistics in terms of three groups with the statistics of the number of test samples. This figure indicates that among the ratio of USA and UK, though the number of test samples of USA is double that of the UK, their difference among death and active cases ratio is lower, which seems not a normal distribution. As the number of test samples is high, and at that time the COVID situation was almost similar in both countries and the samples were taken from the same date and year, in general, the difference between death and active cases in the USA should be quite larger than UK. Besides, if we compare the ratio of the USA and Spain, Spain has 10 times fewer test samples than the USA but unexpectedly each country has the same difference in their death and active case ratio. From this statistic, we can conclude that there is significant under-sampling/under estimation observed in the record of the USA. However, it is important to indicate that, we only consider the SD of group 3, because for group 1 and group 2, the difference was not significant, but for group 3, the difference was significant which is effective to consider for the analysis.

Figure 1: Representation of SD values of the individual group

However, in any pandemic, we observed a lack of attention in the data collection process which increases the possibilities of biased estimation. There is an array of aspects can be seen in the data collection process that can act as an influencing factor for biased estimation such as not considering asymptomatic carriers (those who have never shown symptoms after the onset of infection), lack of testing opportunities, violation of clinical data protection law, vulnerabilities of testing equipment,

underestimate the fatality risk, and unwillingness of attending screening process are prime. Thus, during the data collection process, these aspects might be taken into consideration and should be maintained strictly to avoid any issue related to biased data to overcome the under-sampling problem.

Figure 2: Representation of SD values of three groups with tested samples of each country

Conclusion

According to the findings of our analysis, it seems that in the USA, there has been a significant Under-sampling/reporting issue observed in the total number of detected cases. If the ratio of under-reporting data continues to grow, it will be a significant cause to reduce the effectiveness of the reported cases which could directly affect the reliance of people on the reported cases. However, several causes might act as influence factors. Based on the current descriptive statistics analysis and simple mathematical calculations, it is suggested that data collection should be more sophisticated and should consider patients with lighter symptoms and/or asymptomatic carriers, who may very effectively transmit the virus. In addition, as in this work, we analyzed data from a limited number of countries for a single-day record, thus other countries' data with multiple

time stamps will be considered in our future study to represent a clear scenario of the under-sample/estimation ratio of the reported cases.

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References

- [1] Oladunni, T., Tossou, S., Haile, Y., & Kidane, A. (2021). COVID-19 county level severity classification with imbalanced class: A nearmiss under-sampling approach. *medRxiv*, 2021-05.
- [2] Zhao, H., Lu, X., Deng, Y., Tang, Y., & Lu, J. (2020). COVID-19: asymptomatic carrier transmission is an underestimated problem. *Epidemiology & Infection*, 148.
- [3] Wurtzer, S., Marechal, V., Mouchel, J. M., & Moulin, L. (2020). Time course quantitative detection of SARS-CoV-2 in Parisian wastewaters correlates with COVID-19 confirmed cases. *MedRxiv*, 2020-04.
- [4] Kobayashi, T., Jung, S. M., Linton, N. M., Kinoshita, R., Hayashi, K., Miyama, T., ... & Nishiura, H. (2020). Communicating the risk of death from novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19). *Journal of clinical medicine*, 9(2), 580.
- [5] Burgess, S., Ponsford, M. J., & Gill, D. (2020). Are we underestimating seroprevalence of SARS-CoV-2?. *Bmj*, 370.
- [6] Accorsi, E. K., Qiu, X., Rumpler, E., Kennedy-Shaffer, L., Kahn, R., Joshi, K., ... & Lipsitch, M. (2021). How to detect and reduce potential sources of biases in studies of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 36, 179-196.
- [7] Tolles, J., & Luong, T. (2020). Modeling epidemics with compartmental models. *Jama*, 323(24), 2515-2516.
- [8] Abou-Ismaïl, A. (2020). Compartmental models of the COVID-19 pandemic for physicians and physician-scientists. *SN comprehensive clinical medicine*, 2(7), 852-858.
- [9] Hamzah, F. B., Lau, C., Nazri, H., Ligot, D. V., Lee, G., Tan, C. L., ... & Chung, M. H. (2020). CoronaTracker: worldwide COVID-19 outbreak data analysis and prediction. *Bull World Health Organ*, 1(32), 1-32.
- [10] Shapiro, M. B., Karim, F., Muscioni, G., & Augustine, A. S. (2020). Are we there yet? An adaptive SIR model for continuous estimation of COVID-19 infection rate and reproduction number in the United States. *medRxiv*, 2020-09.
- [11] Hou, C., Chen, J., Zhou, Y., Hua, L., Yuan, J., He, S., ... & Jia, E. (2020). The effectiveness of quarantine of Wuhan city against the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): A well-mixed SEIR model analysis. *Journal of medical virology*, 92(7), 841-848.
- [12] Langousis, A., & Carsteanu, A. A. (2020). Undersampling in action and at scale: application to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment*, 34, 1281-1283.